

Calibration and validation of AquaCrop model for drip irrigated cabbage under semi-arid region of Maharashtra

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted for two years at College of Agricultural Engineering, VNMKV, Parbhani (M.S.) to calibrate and validate an AquaCrop model for cabbage for varying irrigation schedules. Calibration of AquaCrop for drip-irrigated cabbage was tested for its performance under fully irrigated treatment. Part of the obtained field data *i.e.* data for full irrigation treatment (100% ET_c) for first year was used for calibration of the model, while the data of second year was used to validate the model. AquaCrop version 6.0 was used in the study. The model was calibrated with harvesting index of 85% and water productivity 27 g/m². After calibration, AquaCrop model was validated for its performance under deficit and fully irrigated treatments. Validation results indicates that AquaCrop model was predicted well, having only -4.4 per cent average variation between observed and simulated yield with Nash Sutcliffe coefficient (R^2_{NS}) value 0.88 and Coefficient of Residual Mass (CRM) value -0.091, indicates that model overestimates the yield, likewise during calibration.

Keywords: AquaCrop model, calibration, fertigation etc.

Introduction:

The great challenge of the agricultural sector is to produce more food with less water. Irrigated agriculture is the largest water-consuming sector which faces competing demands from other sectors, like industrial and domestic. Increasing demand and scarcity of water makes it important to use available water in most economic and efficient ways. The non-uniform, scarce and ill distribution of natural

precipitation, high evapotranspiration demands and excessive depletion of limited ground water resources is stressing the need of efficient management practices in soil, water and crop to attain higher crop productivity. Thus, there is an urgent need to assess the potential of reducing water needs and increasing production. Aquacrop is a comprehensive crop growth model (FAO, 2017; Steduto et al., 2007; Raes et al., 2007; Hsiao et al. 2007) which addresses

the need by providing a yield response to water simulation with limited sophistication. It also simulates crop yield response to water and is particularly suited to address conditions where water is a key limiting factor in crop production. The capability of AquaCrop is tested and confirmed by various researches throughout the world (Araya *et al.* 2010, Heng *et al.* 2009; Stricevic *et al.* 2011; Abedinpour *et al.* 2012, Andarzian *et al.* 2011 etc). AquaCrop is developed from the revision of ‘FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper No. 33 Yield Response to Water’ (Doorenbos and Kassam, 1979). AquaCrop attempts to balance accuracy, simplicity, and robustness. AquaCrop is the successor of CropWat featuring new adjustment options to reproduce crop environment in more detail. Calibration and validation of AquaCrop for semi-arid regions like Marathwada can be used to predict crop yield and water productivity.

To meet the objectives of present research project field experiment entitled “Precision

Irrigation and Fertigation Management for Cabbage (*Brassica Oleracea var. Capitata*)” was conducted consequently for two rabi seasons in the year 2016-17 and 2017-18 at Research Farm of AICRP on Water Management in Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani.

Methodology:

Brief description AquaCrop model

AquaCrop has a structure that includes the soil, with its water balance; the plant, with its development, growth and yield processes; and the atmosphere, with its thermal regime, rainfall, evaporative demand and carbon dioxide concentration. Additionally, some management aspects are explicitly considered (e.g., irrigation, fertilization, etc.), as they will affect the soil water balance, crop development and therefore final yield. Pests, diseases, and weeds are not considered. The functional relationships between the different model components are depicted in Fig.

FigA. Flow chart of AquaCrop indicating the main components of soil–plant–atmosphere continuum

Data collection and input data parameters

AquaCrop requires following data which were collected and processed as per requirement of model.

Weather data

Weather data for the period 15th January 2016 to 24th April 2017, and 20th January 2018 to 27th April 2018 was obtained from Meteorological

Observatory, VNMKV, Parbhani. It comprised of maximum and minimum temperature (°C), mean daily relative humidity (%), daily sunshine hours (hr), wind speed (ms-1), rainfall (mm) and evaporation (mmday-1).

Crop data

Crop-specific parameters required by AquaCrop model are plant density, yield, biomass, harvest index (HI), effective rooting depth, crop growth stages and green canopy cover (CC), while required user-specific parameters are crop cultivar, timing of crop cycle, water management and agronomic practices. The data was obtained from two years field experiment conducted during the period 14th January 2017 to 24th April 2017, and 20th January 2018 to 27th April 2018.

Soil data

The soil data obtained from the physicochemical analysis of soil samples of experimental plots were used to characterize the soil.

Model setup

The model was setup using creating file menus. Using these menus input files for new climate, crop, irrigation management, soil profile, ground water and field data were created.

Climate file

Climate file consists of creating a temperature file, ET_o file, rain file and CO₂ file. While creating ET_o, rain or temperature file, the type of data (daily, 10-daily or monthly data) and time range was specified.

Crop file

While creating a crop file, type of crop (fruit/grain producing crops, leafy vegetable crops, roots and tubers, or forage crops) and parameters such as planting method, cropping period and length of growing cycle were specified. With the help of this information AquaCrop generates a complete set of required crop parameters. These included the planting dates, seedling emergence, duration of the various cabbage physiological periods from sowing date and harvesting dates. Plant population is based on the recommended plant

spacing for the site. The parameters are displayed and the values can be adjusted in the crop characteristics menu.

Soil profile file

To create a soil profile file, soil characteristics *viz.* soil type, number of horizons and their thickness were specified. With the help of this information AquaCrop generates a complete set of soil profile parameters. The parameters are displayed and the values can be adjusted in the soil profile characteristics menu.

Irrigation file

Type of irrigation file was specified first from the listed below, while creating an irrigation file:

- I. Net irrigation water requirement
- II. Irrigation schedule
- III. Generation of irrigation schedule

Subsequently in accordance to irrigation file specified, the following required information was also specified:

- a) The allowable depletion when determining the net irrigation requirement
- b) The time, application depth and the irrigation water quality of the successive irrigation events
- c) The irrigation water quality, time and depth criteria to generate irrigation events

Groundwater file

While creating groundwater file, type of file (from listed below) was specified first.

- I. Constant depth and water quality or
- II. Variable depth or water quality.

Subsequently, the depth and quality of the groundwater for various moments (if variable) in the season were specified in the Groundwater characteristics menu.

Project file

In project file, type of file was specified first from the listed below.

- I. Single simulation run
- II. Successive years (multiple runs) or
- III. Crop rotation (multiple runs)

After creation of various files, sowing or planting date, simulation period and corresponding initial and off-season conditions

were specified. The characteristics can be updated in the project characteristics menu.

Field data file

When creating a field data file, the observed green canopy cover (CC) on particular dates as obtained from field experiment data was specified in the field data menu.

Calibration and validation of model

Part of the obtained field data *i.e.* data for full irrigation treatment (100% ET_c) for the year 2016-2017 was used for calibration of the model, while the data of 2017-2018 was used to validate the model. AquaCrop version 6.0 was used in the study. The model was calibrated and validated by varying following parameters manually:

- i) Harvest index
- ii) Water productivity (WPb)

AquaCrop version 6.0 was used in the study.

Output extraction

Simulation results are stored in a set of output files. The output files with daily data contain information on the crop development and production.

Model Performance

a) Nash-Sutcliffe coefficient of efficiency

Nash-Sutcliffe coefficient of efficiency (R_{NS}^2) is used to assess predictive power of hydrological models. R_{NS}^2 is described by following formula (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970)

$$R_{NS}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (Q_o - Q_s)^2}{\sum (Q_o - Q_{av})^2} \dots (3.9)$$

Where,

Q_o - observed values

Q_s - simulated values

Q_{av} - mean of observed values

Nash-Sutcliffe coefficient of efficiency can range from $-\infty$ to 1. R_{NS}^2 value of 1 therefore indicate perfect fit. An efficiency of zero indicates that the model predictions are as accurate as the mean of observed data. Closer the model efficiency to 1, more accurate is the

model. Model efficiency less than 0.7 correspond to a very poor fit (Coulibaly *et al.* 2000).

b) Coefficient of Residual Mass (CRM)

Coefficient of Residual Mass (CRM) is a dimensionless statistical performance criteria as described below.

$$CRM = \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^n O_i - \sum_{i=1}^n S_i \right]}{\sum_{i=1}^n O_i} \dots (3.10)$$

Where,

O_i - Observed value at time i

S_i - Simulated value at time i

This criterion indicates the overall under or over-estimation of the ordinates. For a perfect model, the value of CRM is zero. A positive value of CRM indicates the tendency of model to underestimate the observed ordinates, whereas the negative value indicates a tendency to overestimate the observed ordinates.

Results and Discussion:

Calibration of AquaCrop model

In crop simulation models, calibration is necessary to estimate the model parameter values for different crops, cultivars and ecosystems. Model calibration helps in reducing the parameter uncertainty. The experimental data of first crop period (14^h January 2017 to 24th April 2017) was used for calibration of AquaCrop model. The irrigation level I_4 representing full irrigation treatment (100 % of ET_c) was used for this. AquaCrop was calibrated manually by varying model parameters (Art. 3.19.13). These parameters include canopy cover, growth and canopy decline coefficient; crop coefficient for transpiration at full canopy; water productivity (WP); soil water depletion thresholds for inhibition of leaf growth, stomata conductance and acceleration of canopy senescence; and coefficients for adjusting the harvest index (HI) in relation to inhibition of leaf growth and stomata conductance.

Canopy cover:

Canopy parameters such as initial canopy cover, canopy size of transplanted seedling, number of days to recover; maximum canopy cover and

canopy cover decline etc. were adjusted manually during the calibration process. Table 1. presents the observed and simulated canopy cover.

Table 1: Observed and simulated canopy cover during calibration

Day after transplanting	Canopy cover, per cent	
	Observed	Simulated
10	0.7	1.1
20	3.8	4.9
30	16.5	22.9
40	55.8	68
50	68.9	81.3
60	80.7	84.2
70	88.6	84.8
80	86.4	83.8
90	81.4	80.9
R^2_{NS}	0.96	
CRM	-0.060	

Yield of cabbage:

After adjusting the canopy, harvesting index and water productivity were varied manually. Cumulative observed and simulated yield is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Cumulative observed and simulated yield for calibration period

Sr. No.	Treatments	Observed Yield, t ha ⁻¹	Simulated Yield, t ha ⁻¹
1	I ₄ = Drip irrigation at 100 per cent ETc	43.88	44.35

Model generated transpiration, canopy cover and soil moisture in the root zone for drip irrigation level of 1.0 ETc (I₄ for 2017) for calibration period is depicted in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Model generated transpiration, canopy cover and soil moisture in the root zone for drip irrigation level of 1.0 ETc (I₄ for 2017) for calibration period

Above results showed that the model calibration was satisfactory as the observed and simulated values of canopy cover and cabbage yield matched well. Also R_{NS}^2 and CRM statistics were acceptable. Hence, the AquaCrop model setup was considered as calibrated. Calibrated model parameters are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Calibrated model parameters

Description	Measure
A) Canopy cover	
Initial canopy cover (CC_0), %	0.67
Mode of planting	Transplant
Canopy size of transplanted seedling, $cm^2 plant^{-1}$	15.0
Maximum canopy cover, %	85
Plant density, $plant ha^{-1}$	4.4
Canopy decline	Very slow
Day 1 to recovery, days	7
Day 1 to maximum canopy, days	55
Senescence, days	75
Root system	Shallow rooted crop
Maximum effective depth, m	0.3
B) Harvesting index, %	85
C) Water productivity (WP_b), gm^{-2}	27

Model validation:

Without any further adjustments to the calibrated model parameters, the validation of AquaCrop model was carried out. The model was validated for the remaining treatments (I_1 , I_2 , I_3 , and I_5) of first crop season during the period of 14th January to 24th April 2017 and for all the treatments (I_1 to I_5) of second crop season during the period of 20th January to 27th April 2018. For validation period, for each treatment the cumulative yield was simulated with model and presented in Table 4. It also presents the results of statistical tests for validation period.

Table 4: Statistical analysis of validated results for yield

Sr. No.	Crop season	Treatments	Yield, $t ha^{-1}$	
			Observed	Simulated
1	Validation 2017	I_1 = Drip irrigation at 0.4 ETc	27.90	29.77
2		I_2 = Drip irrigation at 0.6 ETc	34.68	32.75
3		I_3 = Drip irrigation at 0.8 ETc	42.64	41.88
4		I_5 = Drip irrigation at 1.2 ETc	38.81	37.38
5	Validation 2018	I_1 = Drip irrigation at 0.4 ETc	23.69	25.85
6		I_2 = Drip irrigation at 0.6 ETc	29.62	28.39
7		I_3 = Drip irrigation at 0.8 ETc	37.15	33.66
8		I_4 = Drip irrigation at 1.0 ETc	38.67	40.86
9		I_5 = Drip irrigation at 1.2 ETc	33.38	35.10
		R_{NS}^2	0.88	
		CRM	-0.091	

The data presented in Table 4, revealed that the simulated and observed values of yield of cabbage matched well for different deficit and full irrigation treatments. The yield of cabbage varied between 23.69 to 42.64 $t ha^{-1}$.

Model generated transpiration, soil moisture and canopy cover in the root zone for drip irrigation at 0.6 ET_c (I₂ for 2017) was narrated in Fig. 2. From the figure it can be revealed that soil moisture in the root zone was at field capacity up to first 30 days. Thereafter, it gradually decreases and further remains more or less constant from 30 to 50 days after transplanting. The soil moisture was within available water capacity throughout the crop period. During first 50 days, the transpiration matched with that for full irrigation schedule (1.0 ET_c). Later on, transpiration was decreased gradually till end of the crop period as compared to that for full irrigation schedule and therefore yield was reduced and simulated as 32.75 t ha⁻¹. The canopy cover was also decreased from 50 to 90 days after transplanting.

Fig. 2: Model generated transpiration, soil moisture and canopy cover in the root zone for drip irrigation at 0.6 ET_c (I₂ for 2017) for validation period

Conclusion:

The model was calibrated with harvesting index of 85 per cent and water productivity 27 g m⁻². The canopy cover and crop yields simulated by AquaCrop model compared reasonably well with the measured data. The Nash Sutcliffe coefficient (R^2_{NS}) and Coefficient of Residual Mass (CRM) for canopy cover predictions were 0.96 and -0.60, respectively with slightly over predictions during 23 to 84 DAP. The predicted yields by the model under deficit and fully irrigated treatments were in close agreement with their measured counterparts under all the treatments with Nash Sutcliffe coefficient (R^2_{NS}) and Coefficient of Residual Mass (CRM) values of 0.88 and -0.091, respectively. The average variation between observed and simulated yield was found to be 4.4 per cent.

AquaCrop model can predict the temporal variation in soil moisture distribution and total water requirement of cabbage reasonably well.

AquaCrop model can favourably simulate the effect of full water and deficit irrigation on cabbage crop growth parameters. The differences between observed and simulated yields are within the acceptable limits.

References:

1. Abedinpour M, Sarangi A, Rajput TBS, Singh, Man, Pathak H, Ahmad T (2012). Performance evaluation of AquaCrop model for maize crop in a semi-arid environment. *Agricultural Water Management*, 110: 55–66.
2. Andarzian A, Bannayan M, Steduto P, Mazraeh H, Barati ME, Barati MA and Rahnema A (2011). Validation and testing of the AquaCrop model under full and deficit irrigated wheat production in Iran. *Agricultural Water Management*, 100: 1–8.
3. Araya A, Habtu S, Hadgu KM, Kebede A and Dejene T (2010). Test of AquaCrop

model in simulating biomass and yield of water deficient and irrigated barley (*Hordeum vulgare*). *Agricultural Water Management*, 97: 1838–1846.

4. Doorenbos J, Kassam AH, and Bentvelsen CIM (1979). Yield response to water, Rome. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
5. Heng LK, Hsiao T, Evett S, Howell T, and Steduto P (2009). Validating the FAO AquaCrop Model for Irrigated and Water Deficient Field Maize. *Agron. J.*, 101: 488-498.
6. Hsiao T, C,L.K. Heng, P. Steduto, B. Rojas-Lara, D. Raes, and E. Fereres (2009). AquaCrop—The FAO Crop Model to Simulate Yield Response to Water: III. Parameterization and Testing for Maize *Agron. J.* 101: 448–459
7. Raes D, Steduto P, Hsiao TC and Fereres E (2009). AquaCropThe FAO Crop Model to Simulate Yield Response to Water: II. Main Algorithms and Software Description. *Agronomy J.*, 101 (3): 438.